

National Institutes of Health

Data management plan required?	Yes (From 1 st October 2003 researchers in receipt of a grant greater than \$500,000 need to include a data management plan or information on why data sharing is not possible. (Also possible for awards < \$500,000))
RDM policy Link	https://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/data_sharing/data_sharing_guidance
Definition of data	Final research data, basic research data, clinical studies, surveys, human and non-human studies, secondary use of data
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	Not specified
Required data repository	Not specified
Time for data release	No later than the acceptance for publication of the final data set (dependent on nature of dataset).
Time for long-term storage of data	3 years since from end of grant
Costings	Researchers can request costs for data management/ sharing/ archiving. For data already collected it is possible to ask for an administrative or competitive supplement.
Last updated	Not known
Contact Details	grantsinfo@od.nih.gov
Comments	N/A

Documents used:

Data sharing guidance https://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/data_sharing/

NIH statement on sharing research data

<https://grants.nih.gov/grants/guide/notice-files/NOT-OD-03-032.html>

Data sharing regulations/ policy/ guidance chart for NIH awards

https://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/data_sharing/data_sharing_chart.doc

FAQ Data sharing https://grants.nih.gov/grants/policy/data_sharing/data_sharing_faqs.htm

Accessed: May 2018